

much divided and from 5 to 25 cm long. Sporocarps are 2 to 3 mm in diameter and sterile. They are found on parts of the submerged leaves.

To our knowledge, this is the first time the weed has been found in rice in the Philippines. *S*

2. Diagram showing floating leaves, submerged leaves, and sporocarps of *S. molesta*.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Herbicides for weed control in rice nurseries

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Effect of herbicide treatments on weed dry weight and rice seedling dry matter yield at 26 d after sowing, Naysari, India.

Treatment ^a	Weed dry wt (g/m ²)	Seedling dry matter yield (g/m ²)
Unweeded control	31	29
Hand weeding 15 DAS	8	47
Propanil 2.0 kg/ha	17	34
Thiobencarb (kg ai/ha)		
1.0	16	32
1.5	16	33
2.0	12	37
Butachlor (kg ai/ha)		
1.0	18	33
1.5	10	34
2.0	9	36
Pendimethalin (kg ai/ha)		
1.0	19	34
1.5	10	44
2.0	6	47
CD at 5%	3	6

^aDAS = days after sowing.

We evaluated five herbicides and application rates for controlling weeds in an IR22 nursery at GAU Farm in 1984 kharif (Jun-Nov). Thiobencarb, butachlor, and pendimethalin were applied at different doses 5 d after sowing, and propanil was applied 15 d after sowing. Samples of weeds and rice seedlings were collected from a 1-m² area 26 d after sowing and dry weight was recorded. Weeds were *Cyperus difformis* and *C. iria* (53%), *Echinochloa spp.* (41%), and *Eclipta alba* (6%).

Butachlor controlled sedges and

pendimethalin controlled monocots. Higher doses of all the herbicides were more effective than lower doses. Only propanil was phytotoxic, causing slight leaf tip burning.

Weed dry weight and dry matter yield of rice seedlings showed a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.73$). Lowest weed dry weight (6 g/m²) and highest seedling dry matter yield (47 g/m²) were with pendimethalin at 2.0 kg ai/ha, closely followed by hand weeding (see table). *S*

Soil and Crop Management

Effect of harvest time on IR44 ratoon grain yield

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Ratoon crop duration is very important for ratoon grain yield. Although an

advantage of a ratoon crop is its short growth duration, sometimes duration is too short for tillers to produce enough leaf area to support a well-filled panicle. The result is low ratoon grain yields. Relatively longer ratoon crop duration contributes to higher grain yield, but if

duration is too long, productivity/ d per ha declines

IR44 is a good ratooning variety, but the ratoon crop has nonsynchronous maturity and its growth duration can be more than 100 d. Nonsynchronous maturity also makes ratoon harvesting difficult.

We studied the effect of harvest time of an IR44 ratoon crop on grain yield in Dec 1983-Jul 1984 at IRRI. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 2 seedlings/hill in a 23.0- × 23.2-m² plot. NPK was applied at 120-13-25 kg/ha. Half of the N and all of P and K were incorporated at final puddling. The remaining N was topdressed at 28 and 40 d after transplanting. At maturity, five 6-m² subplots were sampled for main crop grain yield.

Plants were ratooned by cutting stalks at 15-cm height. Immediately after cutting, 40 kg N/ha was broadcast followed by insecticide spray. The ratoon crop was harvested at 75, 80, 85, and 90 d after main crop harvest (DAH). The 6-m² subplots were sampled at each harvesting date. Ten random plants from each plot were taken to record panicles/plant, spikelets/panicle, and spikelet fertility. Unfilled grains were separated by specific gravity method using saline solution (1.65 kg/ 10 litres of

Effect of harvest time on grain yield and components in an IR44 ratoon crop, IRRI, 1984 dry season. ^a

DAH	Panicles/ plant	Spikelets/ panicle	Spikelet fertility (%)	Fully filled grains(%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (g/m ²)	
						Actual	Adjusted
75	14 ns	61 ns	70 bc	83 b	25 ns	126 b	136 b
80	14	70	67 c	88 a	25	161 a	188 a
85	12	72	73 ab	92 a	25	168 a	196 a
90	13	67	75 a	92 a	25	151 ab	178 a

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ns = nonsignificant.

water). Grain yield at 14% moisture content was recorded and expressed in g/m².

Main crop grain yield was 516 g/m². Ratoon crop harvest time significantly affected spikelet fertility, fully filled grains, and ratoon grain yield (see table). Ratoon grain yield varied from 126 g/m² for 75 DAH to 168 g for 85 DAH. Number of regenerated hills among treatments varied from 86% for 75 DAH to 75% for 90 DAH. Ratoon grain yield was calculated based on maximum recorded regeneration (92%) to eliminate the differences due to number of regenerated hills, which caused large variations in ratoon grain yield and partially concealed the effect of time of harvest.

The lowest grain yield (136 g) was at 75 DAH and the highest at 85 DAH;

however, they were not statistically different from those at 80 and 90 DAH. Spikelet fertility did not differ significantly between 85 and 90 DAH. Spikelet fertility at 75 DAH was at par with that at 80 and 85 DAH. The differences in spikelet fertility did not explain the differences in grain yield. The proportion of fully filled grains was the lowest at 75 DAH.

The differences in fully filled and total spikelets/panicle can explain the differences in grain yield among the treatments. Late tillers with low spikelet number/panicle contributed to low yields in 90 DAH treatment. Shattering of overripe grains also reduced yield. The optimum time of IR44 ratoon crop harvest is 80-85 d after main crop cutting, which is still too long for most situations. *ℓ*

Nitrogen volatilization from fertilizers applied to salt-affected coastal soils

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We studied N volatilization losses from different N fertilizers in upland and lowland salt-affected soils. Volatilized ammonia gas was trapped in a foam pad soaked with dilute sulfuric acid. The foam pad was placed 30 cm above the soil on a grill on top of a perforated cylindrical support. Volatilization was estimated using a standard curve prepared against actual losses estimated for identical field situations.

N at 100 kg/ha was applied as ammonium sulfate (AS), prilled urea

1. Volatilization losses of N from different fertilizers, West Bengal, India. PU = prilled urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, LCU = lac-coated urea, UB = urea briquet, UPP = PU in paper packets, AS = ammonium sulfate.

(PU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), urea briquet (UB) 3 g, and PU (3 g) in paper packets

(UPP) to puddled, waterlogged fields with ECe 3.5 and 7.5 mmho/cm In a pot experiment, AS and PU were applied to